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I-MOVE-COVID-19 Network

**Multidisciplinary European network for research, prevention and control of
the COVID-19 pandemic**

D2.8: COVID-19 European primary care sentinel surveillance: evaluation report

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Version history

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Abbreviations

ARI	Acute respiratory infection
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EU	European Union
GP	General practitioner
ILI	Influenza-like illness
I-MOVE	Influenza – Monitoring Vaccine Effectiveness in Europe
SARS-CoV-2	Severe acute respiratory syndrome – coronavirus 2
VE	Vaccine effectiveness

1 Background

1.1 I-MOVE-COVID-19 study

The aims of the I-MOVE-COVID-19 (Multidisciplinary European network for research, prevention and control of the COVID-19 pandemic) consortium were to obtain epidemiological and clinical information on patients with COVID-19 as well as virological information on severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) (I-MOVE-COVID-19 network, 2020). At the primary care level, I-MOVE-COVID-19 aimed to provide a flexible surveillance platform, adaptable to the epidemiological situation, through primary care surveillance, in order to contribute to the knowledge base, guide patient management, and inform the public health response. This was envisaged to be achieved through adaptation and expansion of the existing I-MOVE influenza primary care network (Valenciano, Ciancio, 2012) to include COVID-19 surveillance.

The second work package (WP2), primary care surveillance for COVID-19, was coordinated by Nivel (Netherlands Institute for Health Services Research). The I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care network comprised nine sentinel surveillance networks in six (EU) member states and the United Kingdom (UK). The laboratory component of the network included regional and national reference centres from the participating countries. While each of the surveillance sites can analyse their data separately, pooling data was foreseen to provide a larger sample size to enable generating hypotheses and to answering study questions with reasonable precision. An overview of current practice at the general practitioner (GP) level as for 15 April 2020 was provided as part of deliverable 2.1 “Review of current practice: Primary care-based surveillance of COVID-19 in Europe”. A protocol for studies using primary care COVID-19 surveillance was submitted under the deliverable 2.3 on 15 June 2020.

One of the tasks under the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project entailed evaluating the participating surveillance systems at the primary care level in order to provide recommendations on how to adapt or set up a surveillance system to rapidly support surveillance in case of a public health emergency. The protocol for surveillance monitoring and evaluation (deliverable 2.4) established the premises to perform this task that had to be carried out throughout the project.

1.2 Objectives evaluation

The main purpose of the final evaluation under this project was to learn about the challenges participating sites faced during the adaptation of a primary care surveillance system to the pandemic progression.

Based on the I-MOVE-COVID-19 surveillance objectives at primary care level (see Section 1.1), the evaluation assessed whether the following objectives were reached while documenting the challenges faced in their implementation during the pandemic progression:

1. Rapidly detect COVID-19 cases attending/consulting practitioners.
2. Describe the suspected and laboratory confirmed cases by time, age group and region, and where possible by symptoms, patient characteristics and potential risk factors, and by virus (clades).

3. Report COVID-19 cases in a timely manner.
4. Generate useful data for public health actions (such as determining the risk factors for disease severity, measuring the effect of intervention).

Ongoing review of the quality of data collected and periodical assessment of the performance of the surveillance system according to its objectives and key attributes was important in order to identify components that needed to be reinforced and take corrective actions. Identifying the surveillance limitations contributed to better interpret the results of the surveillance-based studies meant to provide evidence for prevention and control of the COVID-19 in the population. Lessons learnt from these evaluations provide crucial information on setting up or adapting surveillance systems in case of a future pandemic.

1.3 Evaluation throughout the project

The protocol for surveillance monitoring and evaluation guided the process of monitoring and evaluation as far as the pandemic situation allowed the study sites to perform their surveillance as envisaged at the outset of the project. As the pandemic progressed and endured, while new SARS-CoV-2 variants emerged, sentinel surveillance systems were challenged and impacted by pandemic control measures and changing patient pathways. After the first pandemic wave, the strengths, challenges, and lessons learned of the first rapid adaptations of the study partners' sentinel surveillance systems were reported in a 'lessons learnt paper' (Bagaria, 2022). The experiences from study sites give useful information on the integration of COVID-19 sentinel surveillance with influenza sentinel surveillance systems. Some study sites were successful in integrating (new) sentinel surveillance systems into COVID-19 community testing centres, while other study sites remained sentinel surveillance in primary care. This led, among others, to differences in the pooled population under surveillance. In November 2020, the World Health Organization provided practical considerations for assessing and addressing disruptions in influenza sentinel surveillance systems when extending to COVID-19 (WHO, 2020).

The study sites differed in the adaptations to their sentinel surveillance systems, ranging from minor adaptations to the existing system to establishing completely new routines. Data collection varied significantly between study sites and affected the initial aims of the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project, which challenged the monitoring and evaluation objectives as outlined in the D2.4 protocol. Accordingly, the evaluation as presented in this report will provide a reflection on the initial objectives as much as possible. A rationale for diverging from these initial objectives is detailed in this report.

2 Methods

2.1 Description of participating networks

The participating primary care surveillance networks and their contribution to the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project are briefly described in table 1 and table 2. Note that the number of participating GP practices reflects the situation in 2021. In many countries, dedicated COVID-19 testing hubs were established in 2020, impacting on the data collection for virological surveillance carried out by sentinel GPs prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. In some countries, new sentinel GP data collection systems were established.

Table 1. Description of participating I-MOVE primary care COVID-19 surveillance networks in 2021

Network (country)	Participating Institutes	Coverage or number of participating GP practices
Oxford-RCGP RSC (England), SARS CoV-2 swab testing was performed in the Respiratory Virus Unit, UKHSA Colindale and at dedicated COVID-19 community testing centres	Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC); Royal College of General Practitioners (RCGP); University of Oxford (UOXF)	134 virology sampling practices of 1,700*
Réseau Sentinelles (France)	Sorbonne Université (SU); Institut Pasteur (IP)	~ 600 practices
Irish sentinel GP network (Ireland)	Health Service Executive (HSE)	61 practices
Navarra (Spain)	Organismo Autónomo Instituto de Salud Pública Y Laboral de Navarra	53
Nivel Primary Care Database - Sentinel Practices (Netherlands), virological testing of the samples is performed at the RIVM	Netherlands Instituut voor Onderzoek van de Gezondheidszorg (Nivel); Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM)	~ 40 practices
Rede Médicos-Sentinel (Portugal)	Instituto Nacional de Saude dr. Ricardo Jorge (INSA)	13 COVID-19 centres for medical consultation and testing of ARI patients
NHS community pathways, primarily comprising COVID-19 community assessment centres and triage hubs (Scotland)	NHS National Services Scotland (NHSNS)	~ 14 NHS Boards across Scotland
Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections (Spain)	Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII)	287 practices (GPs and paediatricians) in five regions
Sentinelövervakning /Sentinel Surveillance Network (Sweden)	Folkhälsomyndigheten (FOHM)	~ 37 practices

* From January 2021 onwards only the sentinel virological surveillance information for England was included.

Table 2. Site-specific surveillance websites of participating I-MOVE primary care COVID-19 networks

Network (country)	URL
RCGP RSC (England)	www.rcgp.org.uk/rsc https://orchid.phc.ox.ac.uk/index.php/cov-19/ https://orchid.phc.ox.ac.uk/index.php/rcgp-rsc/
Réseau Sentinelles (France)	https://www.sentiweb.fr/france/en/?page=bulletin
Irish sentinel GP network (Ireland)	www.hpsc.ie
Navarra (Spain)	http://www.navarra.es/home_es/Gobierno+de+Navarra/Organigrama/Los+departamentos/Salud/Organigrama/Estructura+Organica/Instituto+Navarro+de+Salud+Publica/Publicaciones/Publicaciones+profesionales/Epidemiologia/InformesVigilanciaEpidemiologia2021.htm
Nivel Primary Care Database - Sentinel Practices (Netherlands)	www.nivel.nl/surveillance https://www.rivm.nl/griep-grieprik/feiten-en-cijfers
Rede Médicos-Sentinela (Portugal)	www.insa.min-saude.pt/category/informacao-e-cultura-cientifica/publicacoes/atividade-gripal/
NHS COVID-19 community assessment centres and triage hubs (Scotland)	www.hps.scot.nhs.uk/web-resources-container/enhanced-surveillance-of-covid-19-in-scotland-community-surveillance-protocol/
SiVIRA: Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections (Spain)	https://www.isciii.es/QueHacemos/Servicios/VigilanciaSaludPublicaRENAVE/EnfermedadesTransmisibles/Paginas/VIGILANCIA-CENTINELA-DE-INFECION-RESPIRATORIA-AGUDA.aspx
Sentinelövervakning /Sentinel Surveillance Network (Sweden)	https://www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se/smittskydd-beredskap/overvakning-och-rapportering/sentinelovervakning/

2.2 Data collection

The evaluation was carried out throughout the duration of the project and collated for the final evaluation in this report. Data collection and analysis encompassed a mixed methods approach according to the steps as depicted in figure 1, where steps 1-4 reflect the data collection process, and steps 5 and 6 were iterative in response to the information collected. Sources for the evaluation included project deliverables for work package 2 and additional surveillance bulletins; meeting minutes; data extracts for surveillance; a survey administered in the final phase of the project; and group discussions within the work package coordination team.

Figure 1. Steps in information collection

2.2.1 Document review and meeting notes

Documents that were reviewed for the evaluation included the work package 2 deliverables, minutes from periodically held (online) meetings with the project team (study sites participating in primary care surveillance and the work package 2 coordinators from Epiconcept and Nivel), and steering group meetings (work package leaders from all work packages in the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project), notes from bilateral meetings and emails between study sites and the project coordination team.

2.2.2 Monitoring data

Monitoring data collection of the I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care surveillance was guided by a set of indicators that were proposed in D2.4 'Monitoring & evaluation protocol'. Data extracts were bimonthly provided by the countries and subsequently checked and validated by Epiconcept in cooperation with the study sites. Quantitative evaluation of the final pooled primary care surveillance data set, covering the period March 2020 to the end of December 2021, was performed using Stata (version 16.1).

2.2.3 Survey

Subsequent to the final data extract within the I-MOVE-COVID-19 study, a survey was administered among the study site focal points to gather their reflections and experiences with regard to the performance of the primary care surveillance system in their country (or region) and the project. The study site focal points were asked to rate the performance of surveillance system attributes (according to Marbus et al. 2020; CDC, 2018; ECDC, 2014) on a five-point scale ranging from 1 (poor) to 5 (excellent) and reflect on this rating. The attributes are listed in table 3.

Table 3. Surveillance attributes

Surveillance attribute	Description
Data quality	The completeness and validity of the data recorded in the surveillance system, including the addition of virological diagnostics.
Timeliness	The speed between steps in a surveillance system, from event occurrence, recognition, report, to control and prevention activities.
Representativeness	The ability to accurately describe the occurrence of an event over time, place and person.
Simplicity	The system's structure and ease of operation.
Flexibility	The ability to adapt to changing information needs or technological operating conditions.
Acceptability	The willingness of persons and organisations to participate in the system.
Stability	The system's reliability (ability to collect, manage and provide data without failure) and availability (ability to be operational when needed).
Sustainability	The ongoing maintenance and support of a routine epidemiologic and/or virological surveillance system.

In addition, study site focal points were questioned about the surveillance system adaptations, their experiences and reflections of the whole project, reflections and recommendations for future preparedness of respiratory sentinel surveillance, and their perceived strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats with regard to the project. Except for the attribute ratings, the survey included open-ended questions only (please refer to annex 3 for the questionnaire).

2.3 Data extraction and analysis

The document review was guided by the performance attributes of surveillance systems (Marbus et al. 2020; CDC, 2018; ECDC, 2014), that were included in a data extraction form to collate relevant information. The initial phase in the pandemic and the project was evaluated and reported in a lessons learnt paper (Bagaria, 2022), which provided a starting point for the current evaluation. Particularly the meeting minutes of work package meetings provided information about the set-up of and adaptations to the surveillance systems, and challenges that study sites faced. The survey data were synthesized using a data extraction form and subsequently analysed.

The pooled dataset, including data from all study sites for the whole study period, was analysed using descriptive statistics. Analysis was conducted using Stata 16.

2.4 Feedback to study sites

Throughout the project, study sites were closely involved in checking and validating their data by the work package coordinating team. This monitoring function was in place for the total duration of the project. During the regularly held online meetings, general findings of data monitoring were

discussed with the study sites. Moreover, these meetings were used for sharing experiences and best practices, and solving difficulties. The preliminary results of the final evaluation were shared with study sites at the annual I-MOVE-COVID-19 meeting. The report was circulated among all the I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care members for verification of the findings before finalising the report.

3 Results

3.1 Deliverables

During the project, the deliverables of work package 2 were all met. Additional to the formal deliverables, two interim surveillance bulletins were released, a paper regarding the lessons learnt from sentinel surveillance system changes was submitted to Eurosurveillance, and a poster presentation was submitted to the ISIRV-WHO conference (table 4).

Table 4. Deliverables for primary care surveillance

Deliverable	Submitted
D2.1 Report describing current COVID-19 surveillance practices and recommendations	✓ 15 Apr 2020
D2.2 Capacity strengthening plan	Cancelled
D2.3 Phased surveillance protocol	✓ 15 Jun 2020
D2.4 Surveillance monitoring and evaluation protocol	✓ 15 Jul 2020
D2.5 First surveillance bulletin including data from all sentinel sites	✓ 15 Sep 2020
D2.6 Second surveillance bulletin including data from all sentinel sites	✓ 15 Mar 2021
Additional: Additional Surveillance bulletin January – April 2021	✓ 16 Jul 2021
Additional: poster presentation ISIRV-WHO	✓ 15 Oct 2021
Additional: Additional Surveillance bulletin May – August 2021	✓ 2 Dec 2021
D2.7 Third surveillance bulletin including data from all sentinel sites	✓ 15 Mar 2022
Additional: Paper ‘Rapidly adapting primary care sentinel surveillance across seven countries in Europe for COVID-19 in the first half of 2020: strengths, challenges, and lessons learnt’ (accepted by Eurosurveillance)	✓ 28 Mar 2022

3.2 Description of primary care sentinel surveillance systems in 2021

Throughout the study period and as the pandemic progressed, study sites adapted their sentinel surveillance routines, as will be discussed in the subsequent paragraph. In this paragraph, the current situation of the study sites at the time of the final surveillance bulletin (deliverable D2.7, March 2022) is described. In table 5, the main characteristics of the study sites are listed.

England (EN) – Data was collected from the virology sampling sentinel GP practices participating in the RCGP RSC (Royal College of General Practitioners Research and Surveillance Centre) network. For surveillance purposes, data was collected from patients with symptoms consulting their GP with a diagnosis of "COVID-19", "COVID-19 illness" or "Main symptom" (i.e. presenting with fever, cough, loss of sense of smell, or loss of sense of taste), using an ontological approach, and tested for positive for SARS-CoV-2. Records of subsequent positive SARS-CoV-2 tests were excluded.

France (FR) – Data was collected from all patients with an acute respiratory infection (ARI) consulting in primary care with GPs participating in the Sentinelles network. Since week 21 2020, the national testing strategy implemented by public health authorities recommended that all patients consulting in primary care with COVID-19 symptoms should be referred to a medical lab for SARS-CoV-2 testing. Thus, since then, the routine Sentinelles data collection has been adapted, with Sentinel GPs reporting more information on symptoms and comorbidities, as well as the results of SARS-CoV-2 diagnostic tests (RT-PCR or antigen test, conducted in medical laboratories, or during the GP consultation). Information on other respiratory viruses was not collected.

Ireland (IE) – At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, virological surveillance with the Irish sentinel GP network was disrupted, when face to face GP consultations were stopped. All patients with COVID-19 like symptoms were advised to consult their GP via phone. Virological surveillance with the sentinel GP network was re-established in November 2020, including all COVID-19 phone consultations to the sentinel GP network. Surveillance of COVID-19 with the Irish sentinel GP network was integrated into the national COVID-19 referral pathway, with all patients with COVID-19 symptoms referred to COVID-19 community testing centres for swabbing. Sentinel GP specimens were identified and routed directly to the National Virus Reference Laboratory for SARS-CoV-2 testing. The subset of COVID-19 referral patients who also met the influenza-like illness (ILI) case definition were tested for SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV and other respiratory viruses. Data reported included all patients meeting the Irish COVID-19 case definition and consulting (via phone) a sentinel GP in Ireland. Sentinel GP patients without COVID-19 symptoms were excluded.

Navarra (NA) – The data was collected from ARI patients in primary care from all the Navarra population. Since week 20 in 2020, all outpatients with COVID-19 symptoms have been tested. From all outpatients, information on demographic characteristics, major chronic conditions, influenza and COVID-19 vaccination status, variant and sequencing of viruses was collected. Patients with prior SARS-CoV-2 infection were excluded.

Netherlands (NL) – The routine influenza surveillance system in sentinel primary care practices was continued, with all samples for influenza and other respiratory viruses. Additional testing for SARS-CoV-2 was introduced in March 2020. From 1 June 2020, every citizen with any respiratory symptom can request a diagnostic (PCR or rapid antigen) test at dedicated testing centres. Therefore, the number of ILI/ARI patients in primary care eligible for swabbing has decreased considerably and may not be representative for all persons suspected of COVID-19.

Portugal (PT) – A new sentinel surveillance system was set up, based on a selection of ARI cases among patients visiting primary care centres with respiratory symptoms. Cases were selected using a systematic sampling method (five cases/week per centre). Laboratory data for SARS-CoV-2 and

influenza were available for all cases. Information on underlying chronic diseases and medication were available through data linkage.

Scotland (SC) - The routine GP Sentinel Swabbing Scheme for influenza was stepped down as consultations stopped at practice level. Instead, dedicated NHS COVID-19 triage hubs and community assessment centres were set up across Scotland. From June 2020, patients who were unwell in the community with symptoms compatible with COVID-19 were referred for NHS clinical assessment, either in person or over the telephone. These patients were offered a diagnostic COVID-19 test and asked to provide information about themselves to Public Health Scotland (self-reported by the patient or supplied by the clinical assessment centre) for COVID-19 surveillance purposes. Those patients for whom a test result and enhanced surveillance data were available were included in the community surveillance dataset.

Spain (ES) – The well-consolidated Spanish Influenza Sentinel Surveillance System in primary care was disrupted with the emergence of COVID-19 pandemic, just when the influenza season 2019-20 was almost finishing in Spain. Because of surveillance work since June 2020, a new Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections in Primary Care has been implemented in Spain. For the purpose of primary care surveillance reporting, data from three Spanish regions were included at first, although other regions joined later and more are already working and will participate in a near future (six sentinel regional networks in June 2022). Data from all ARI cases consulting sentinel primary care were collected with information on sex, age, symptoms and presumption of ILI. Respiratory swabs were systematically taken from the first two to five ARI patients per week. From those swabbed patients, information on chronic diseases, SARS-CoV-2, influenza and RSV virological data, and influenza and COVID-19 vaccination was collected. Improving completeness of variables was still ongoing in the final phase of the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project.

Sweden (SE) – Data and samples for both enhanced and aggregated surveillance were collected on all patients with ILI and ARI who consulted a sentinel physician. The existing influenza sentinel surveillance system was expanded in week 10 of 2020 to include COVID-19. While the influenza sentinel surveillance phased out in week 16 of 2020, the COVID-19 sentinel surveillance remained active throughout 2020. During the first wave in 2020, sentinel practices had exclusive access to COVID-19 testing for health workers and those with moderate or severe illness. This led to increased numbers attending for consultation with a three-fold increase in sentinel samples taken. Generalised access to testing from June 2020 led to major declines in participating practices. Efforts were ongoing to encourage GPs to participate given access to both influenza and COVID-19 testing and financial reimbursement for the first five swabs taken per week. In 2021 the sentinel surveillance returned to the seasonal design and paused between week 20 and week 40.

Table 5. Main characteristics of I-MOVE primary care COVID-19 surveillance systems, 2021

Network (country)	Case definition*	Testing strategy
RCGP RSC (England)	ILI or ARI	Sentinel testing
Réseau Sentinelles (France)	ARI	All patients
Irish sentinel GP network (Ireland)	ARI or ILI**	All patients meeting the COVID-19 case definition are tested for SARS-CoV-2. All patients meeting the influenza case definition are tested for SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV and other respiratory viruses.
Navarra (Spain)	ARI	All outpatients with COVID-19 symptoms
Nivel Primary Care Database - Sentinel Practices (Netherlands)	ILI or ARI	Systematic sample
Rede Médicos-Sentinela (Portugal)	ARI	All patients, but a systematic sample is provided for the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project
NHS COVID-19 community assessment centres and triage hubs (Scotland)	ILI or ARI or altered sense of smell/taste	All patients are tested, but only those for whom enhanced surveillance data are also available are included in the community surveillance programme.
Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections (Spain)	ARI	Systematic sample
Sentinelövervakning /Sentinel Surveillance Network (Sweden)	ILI or ARI	Systematic sample

* ILI = influenza-like illness; ARI = acute respiratory infection

** Irish case definitions: www.hpsc.ie/a-z/respiratory/coronavirus/novelcoronavirus/casedefinitions/covid-19interimcasedefinitionforireland/ (COVID-19) and www.hpsc.ie/a-z/respiratory/influenza/casedefinitions/ (influenza)

3.3 Surveillance system adaptations

The study sites adapted the generic primary care surveillance protocol to their specific situation and adapted their primary care sentinel surveillance system accordingly. The range of system changes the sites implemented varied across study sites and ranged from minor amendments to major alterations. After the first pandemic phase, encompassing pre-pandemic (influenza sentinel surveillance structures before March 2020); peak of COVID-19 first wave (March to May 2020; and the post first wave peak surveillance (June to September 2020), an evaluation of the system changes, strengths, challenges and lessons learnt was conducted and reported in a paper for Eurosurveillance (Bagaria, 2022). The changes of the first phase are copied from this paper and reported in paragraph 3.3.1, the adaptations that were issued later in the pandemic are discussed in paragraph 3.3.2.

3.3.1 Primary system adaptations during the first pandemic phase

Changes in the first pandemic phase from March to September 2020 were mostly in patient pathways, sampling criteria, decentralisation of laboratory capacity, and data collection. The degree of adaptations to the main areas of change are listed in table 6. Note that two study sites are not represented in this overview, being the Spanish region of Navarra and Ireland (in the process of adapting the Irish sentinel surveillance system at the time of data collection). The system changes by study site during this initial phase of the pandemic are reported in annex 1.

Table 6. Most commonly adapted aspects to sentinel surveillance by country, degree of change (March – September 2020)

Country	Degree of adaptations			
	Patient pathway	Sampling criteria	Laboratories	Data collection
Sweden	+	=	=	=
Netherlands	++	=	=	=
France	++	++	++	++
England	++	++	++	+
Portugal	+++	+++	+++	++
Scotland	+++	++	+++	+++
Spain	+++	+++	+++	+++

Legend: no changes: =; minor changes: +; modest changes: ++; major changes: +++

3.3.1.1 Patient pathway

During the peak of the first pandemic wave, the number of people attending primary care decreased and parallel testing routes facilitated generalised access to testing. This and greater use of telemedicine led to declines in primary care consultations. Therefore, the number of sentinel swabs collected through primary care in all countries decreased. Response to this varied across countries, with differences in balancing diagnostic testing and testing for sentinel surveillance.

In Sweden, initially COVID-19 testing was only available for healthcare workers and those with moderate or severe illness, resulting in patients with mild or no symptoms attending GPs to use the sentinel system for COVID-19 testing. Generalised access to testing from June onwards led to major declines in participating practices. In the Netherlands, patient pathways changed and diminished the number of swabs taken in sentinel surveillance. Firstly, GPs were organized in COVID-19 conglomerates, thus reducing the number of GPs seeing symptomatic patients. Since GPs were only able to submit sentinel swabs for their own patients, the number of sentinel swabs collected declined. From June onwards, symptomatic patients were redirected from GPs to generalised testing by municipal health services.

In France, the number of sentinel practices did not change, however more patients could be recruited due to a change of case definition in March 2020. Moreover, patient recruitment pathways changed in May 2020 when the sentinel swabbing system ended as free access to COVID-19 testing was generalized and SARS-CoV-2 status could be reported for all patients consulting in sentinel practices and responding to the case definition.

England trebled the number of sentinel practices. Patient pathways changed, with swabs either taken by a clinician or via self-swabs by the patient. The sentinel system has also adapted to extend

its serology surveillance. England added a self-swabbing pathway for patients to sample at home to it in-practice sampling.

In Scotland, GPs were no longer able to carry out swabs in their usual settings, but patients were identified using a new centralised telephone triage pathway. Patients were either referred to local telephone based COVID-19 hubs for a self-swab and home care, or for a face-to-face GP assessment and swab at local COVID-19 assessment centres. Later, as new COVID-19-specific diagnostic laboratories were set up for the general public, the system was amended to allow inclusion of samples collected in these parallel testing units in the enhanced surveillance system.

Portugal and Spain ended sentinel surveillance for all respiratory infections including influenza. In Portugal, the focus was shifted to diagnosis of COVID-19 cases in reference hospitals and later in COVID-19 centres supported by private laboratories. In Spain, diagnosis was extended to primary care physicians and COVID-19 testing units. In Spain, relocation of GPs to different PC centers or hospitals and the widespread use of telephone consultations during the most intense weeks of the pandemic led to declines in the numbers of swabs taken by participating practices. From October 2021, after one pilot 2020-21 season of a new sentinel ARI surveillance system, virological testing circuits were fully defined in participating regions, and the objectives of an integrated respiratory system were met, allowing the monitoring of influenza, COVID-19 and RSV.

3.3.1.2 Sampling criteria

Scotland, England, and Portugal swabbed using the WHO COVID-19 case definition. France amended influenza sampling criteria from ILI syndromic surveillance to ARI. Spain first used the WHO ARI case definition, and then moved to weekly extractions of ARI ICD-10 codes from primary care electronic records, with a systematic sampling and testing of the first two to five ARI consulting per GP per week. Both Sweden and the Netherlands maintained their original sampling strategy. All countries continued with face-to-face swabbing by physicians and in some cases practice nurses. However, only England and Scotland employed the use of self-swabbing for sentinel surveillance.

3.3.1.3 Laboratories

Prior to COVID-19, each of the countries tested sentinel swabs in centralised reference laboratories for influenza virus. England, Sweden and the Netherlands continued to test all sentinel samples at the reference laboratories. In the Netherlands, the number of specimens was too low to be meaningful due to generalised testing of symptomatic patients at municipal health services. The laboratory capacity was increased and decentralised for SARS-CoV-2 testing. All the other surveyed countries shifted either during or after the peak to decentralised testing, and increased laboratory capacity to test sentinel samples for COVID-19. France first continued to use three reference laboratories, but later decentralised testing outside the Sentinelles network consistent with the national testing strategy. Portugal decentralised testing during the first pandemic phase (March – September 2020) and made diagnostic testing available to the general population on request from a physician. In Scotland, testing policy was changed from surveillance to diagnostic testing. All regional health boards were asked to test and process COVID-19 samples from their region through local labs, helping reduce turnaround time. In addition, new laboratories dedicated exclusively to COVID-19 testing were implemented. In Spain, SARS-CoV-2 testing was extended to all regional laboratories with diagnostic capacity during the first pandemic phase. Some of them were into the previous influenza reference laboratory network and many others were new laboratories for COVID-19

testing. Finally, specific circuits for sentinel ARI surveillance in primary care were set up for surveillance of influenza, COVID-19 and RSV.

3.3.1.4 Data collection and digital technology

The use of digital technology for patient consultations, patient data entry, and reporting of results increased across the study period. Portugal shifted to online data collection during the first pandemic wave and France made amendments to their data collection. In France, Portugal and Scotland centralised databases for nationwide collection of COVID-19 results were implemented. Spain adapted the former Web application of the Spanish Influenza Sentinel Surveillance System to include data from ARI sentinel surveillance in Primary Care. From January 2022, a new Web platform of the Acute Respiratory infection Surveillance System (SiVIRA) is working to collect data from ARI and SARI sentinel surveillance systems in primary care and hospitals. In SiVIRA, electronic reporting of clinical and virological data is being promoted at regional level, to achieve the maximum automation of surveillance processes. In Portugal, the National Surveillance System (SINAVE) was used for clinical, epidemiological, and laboratory data collection. In France and Scotland, information was sent directly to both the patient and the physician. In England, results from September 2020 onwards were sent via e-Labs, an electronic laboratory reporting system. Data from parallel national testing sites set up to allow generalised access to COVID-19 testing were shared with GPs for entry into a central database and inclusion in sentinel surveillance. In the Netherlands, although not sentinel based, digital technology was developed for making testing appointments, collecting basic consultation data, collecting and reporting testing data, and testing results feedback to patients and GPs. The system centralised country-wide collating of all data and production of weekly reports, including sentinel GP data.

3.3.2 Secondary adaptations to surveillance systems

After the initial surge of COVID-19 and adaptations to the sentinel surveillance systems, the pandemic situation kept on evolving rapidly throughout 2020 and 2021. New virus variants emerged, multiple vaccines and self-testing became available, posing new challenges on primary care surveillance. Whereas some study sites continued routines after initial adaptations, others changed routines more than once.

In 2021, data collection changed for a number of sites due to disrupted patient pathway in one study site due to redirecting patients to walk-in COVID-19 testing centres for a delineated period. One study site paused surveillance between week 20 and week 40. One of the sites was overwhelmed by the large number of cases that caused temporal partial collapse of the surveillance system. Yet another site reported that the COVID-centres from which they received data for surveillance were closed and that new sentinel GPs and health centres are currently recruited to revive sentinel surveillance. Additionally, data collection was extended by vaccination information, additional variables, additional regions, data linkage of registry data, an additional questionnaire or extension of testing for other pathogens in addition to SARS-CoV-2. One site reported to have extended data collection with structural whole genome sequencing. Improving data quality for all data sources was mentioned by another study site. One study site noted that the size of the dataset, speed of analysis and data linkage, and serology data collection were improved. One site switched from nasopharyngeal to saliva samples, with possibility of self-sampling after the consultation with the GP in sentinel surveillance.

Main drivers for these adaptations that study sites reported were: striving for higher completeness and validity of data and the need to include COVID-19 vaccination data for the vaccine effectiveness (VE) studies (provide data for VE mentioned as driver three times); new participating regions and a new online platform that enables weekly surveillance reporting and data transfer to ECDC/Epiconcept; envisaged closing of community testing centres and the WHO advice for integration of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance with influenza surveillance (mentioned twice); decreased use of contact tracing system (for which patients were identified from surveillance); the need for good quality data to inform public health interventions and pandemic control; and, increasing acceptability for patients and physicians to participate in virological surveillance to increase sample size.

Regarding data collection, the variables collected changed over time for most study sites. For instance, COVID-19 vaccination status and vaccine product were added by all study sites. Some variables were omitted during the course of the pandemic, for instance to relieve workload of data collection (when questionnaires were used). Some sites amended the instructions to GPs for swabbing, for instance restrictions on the number of patients swabbed, the sampling method, or the case definition.

3.4 Data quality

3.4.1 Variable completion of participating study sites

The evaluation of data quality was based on the pooled surveillance dataset with data collected by all study sites on COVID-19 cases during the period March 2020 – December 2021.

According to the generic protocol for COVID-19 surveillance in primary care, 41 variables were requested on:

- unique identifiers for study site, GP and individual records (N=3)
- patient demographics (age, sex, geographic region; N=3)
- information on consultation (type, date; N=2)
- risk factors (healthcare worker, smoking status, pregnancy, travel history; N=5)
- selected underlying chronic conditions (obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, chronic pulmonary disease, asthma, cancer, immunodeficiency; N=7)
- seasonal influenza and pneumococcal vaccination (N=2)
- COVID-19 signs or symptoms and date of onset (N=16)
- referral to hospital (N=1)
- date of swabbing and laboratory test result for SARS-CoV-2 (N=2)

In addition, 25 optional variables could be collected for surveillance:

- additional clinical signs/symptoms (N=9)
- laboratory test results for other respiratory pathogens (influenza, RSV, rhinovirus, human metapneumovirus, adenovirus, seasonal coronaviruses, bocavirus; N=7)
- type and place of swabbing, type of COVID-19 test (N=3)
- additional chronic conditions (N=4)
- dates of most recent seasonal influenza and pneumococcal vaccination (N=2)

In addition, 31 optional variables could be collected for the risk factor and VE studies:

- further patient characteristics (urbanisation level residence, deprivation score; N=2)

- antiviral administration before swabbing (N=1)
- presymptomatic medication/vaccinations (N=10)
- information on previous positive SARS-CoV-2 infections (tested, quarantine/self-isolate without test, type of test, date of test; N=4)
- antibody test and date (N=2)
- functional status (needing help to bathe or walk; N=2)
- health care utilization in the previous 12 months (GP visits, hospital admissions due to underlying conditions; N=2)
- death (N=1)
- ethnicity (N=1)
- exposure-related factors (close contacts plus setting(s), crowds plus settings, household size, precautions/protective measures; N=6)

When vaccines against COVID-19 became available, these variables were added to the protocol for COVID-19 VE studies (vaccine doses plus dates and brands, booster, target group for booster; N=9 requested, N=5 optional).

Annex 2 gives an overview of the variables for COVID-19 surveillance in primary care. Due to changes in the sentinel surveillance systems, there were differences in variables collected by the study sites. In total, 11 of 41 requested variables could be collected at any time during the project by all study sites. During reporting, some new variables were derived, combining information from different variables collected by study sites. For instance, a variable on 'any chronic condition', based on the presence of four main conditions: lung disease (including or not asthma), heart disease (including or not hypertension), immunodeficiency (including taking immunosuppressive therapy), or diabetes. For some other variables, results were restricted to those study sites that collected the information. All study sites were able to report on COVID-19 vaccination.

3.4.2 Data completeness

Data completeness was evaluated for the requested variables (table 7). Demographic information from COVID-19 cases was almost complete, while risk factors as smoking status, pregnancy status and travelling abroad were poorly completed. Information on underlying chronic conditions was in general available for more than 90% of cases. Date of onset of symptoms was not collected in the Spanish region of Navarra. Since this study site provided the majority of cases, the completeness of this variable was low (11.7%). When we exclude the data from Navarra, completeness for date of onset was 80.6%. Symptoms were not provided by the study sites from England and Navarra, resulting in low percentages of completeness. Restricting the data to study sites that were able, at any time, to collect symptoms, the completeness of symptom reporting ranged from 22.8% for chills to 89.9% for cough. The case-definition for ILI was not used (anymore) in three study sites, resulting in poor completeness of this variable. Information on the ARI case definition was complete for almost all patients (97.5%).

Table 7. Completeness of variables collected for pooled surveillance of 94,678 COVID-19 cases, March 2020 – December 2021

Variable	Not collected (N)	Unknown (N)	Completeness (%)
Age	-	4	100.0
Sex	-	67	99.9
Region	18,313	-	80.7
Health care worker	4,977	6,718	87.7
Smoking status	2,052	55,964	9.5
Pregnancy status ¹	24,618	343	13.0
Travelled in the past 14 days	94,460	18	0.2
Obesity ²	465	3,353	96.0
Diabetes and endocrine disease	465	2,227	97.2
Immunodeficiency (disease or therapy) and organ transplant	465	2,457	97.0
Lung disease	465	2,625	96.7
Asthma	8,308	450	90.8
Cancer	3,957	2,114	93.6
Heart disease	465	3,504	95.8
Having any chronic condition	-	3,795	96.0
Having any of common chronic conditions: lung disease (incl or not asthma), heart disease (incl or not hypertension), immunodeficiency (incl therapy), diabetes	-	1,333	98.6
Received influenza vaccination in current season	90	5,241	94.4
Received pneumococcal vaccination	-	-	-
Received any COVID-19 vaccination ³	-	745	98.5
Date of onset of symptoms	80,917	2,668	11.72
Fever	82,243	319	12.8
Malaise	86,217	145	8.8
Myalgia	86,217	144	8.8
Cough	82,243	233	12.9
Sore throat	82,243	311	12.8
Sudden onset	85,892	34	9.2
Headache	82,243	288	12.8
Shortness of breath	82,243	703	12.4
Has loss of sense of smell/taste	82,352	398	12.6
Fatigue	86,024	243	8.9
Coryza	89,784	109	5.1
Chest pain	89,965	109	4.9
Chills/feverishness	91,574	9	3.3
Meets ILI case definition	-	86,035	9.1
Meets ARI case definition	-	2,327	97.5
Referral of patient to hospital for COVID-19	87,021	336	7.7
Type of consultation	90,193	972	3.7
Swabbing date	-	-	100.0

¹ Restricted to 48,783 COVID-19 cases in the period July 2021 – December 2021.

² Vaccination status at time of swabbing, when the patient was not necessarily part of the target group for vaccination in their country.

³ Restricted to 48,783 COVID-19 cases in the period July 2021 – December 2021. Vaccination status at time of swabbing, when the patient was not necessarily part of the target group for vaccination in their country.

3.4.3 Timeliness

The frequency of reporting about the surveillance results was aimed for months 6, 12 and 24 of the project. Extra surveillance reports were published in months 16 and 21. This planned frequency should be taken into consideration when looking at the timeliness of reporting.

The time between the date the cleaned, pooled dataset was received for analysis by Nivel and the date of publication of the surveillance bulletins ranged from 4 to 19 days. Preparation time for the surveillance bulletin was on average 14 days for the first four reports. For the last report, preparation time was only four days, because the variables in the pooled dataset were comparable to the previous one and the lay-out figures in the report were comparable.

The time between last date of swabbing and date of publication for the five consecutive surveillance reports were 47 days, 40 days, 77 days, 96 days and 70 days, respectively.

3.5 Reflections on the attributes of the surveillance systems: fitness for purpose and use

In this section, the findings from the document review and survey are discussed by attribute of the I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care surveillance. The attributes are evaluated by each of the study sites for their site, in relation to the project. Please note that it may have been difficult, if not impossible, to disentangle the performance of the sites' national surveillance systems from the surveillance objective for the project. All study sites' focal points (N=9) returned the questionnaire.

The study sites rated the performance of the attributes on a five-point scale (ranging from 1-poor to 5-excellent) for both project years separately, and described why this rating reflected the system's performance with regard to the particular attribute. The study sites evaluated overall performance of the process of surveillance and data extraction for the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project generally positive, given the circumstances of changed patient pathways and limitations of data collection.

3.5.1 Data quality

The performance of the primary care surveillance regarding data quality entails the completeness and validity of the data recorded in the surveillance system, including the addition of virological diagnostics. The assumption was that the generic protocol for data collection would be slightly adapted by study sites and that they would provide data according to more or less similar protocols. Experiences with I-MOVE-influenza proved that the data flow worked well. For I-MOVE-COVID-19 however, this user-friendly dataflow resulted in substantial differences in data provided by study sites in terms of formats, coding, data structure, and variables collected. Therefore, this approach yielded quite some work in data validation and recoding for the project coordinating team, which was challenged even more by the rapidness of reporting in I-MOVE-COVID-19.

Two sites rated their system's performance on data quality in the first year of the project excellent, two rated four points, four sites rated three points, and one site rated two points. For the second year, four sites evaluated that their data quality improved with one point, leaving three points as lowest rating. Facilitators for data quality that were mentioned were individualised review of cases by medical doctors as opposed to automatic review of cases. Similarly, data being provided by the GPs themselves merited data quality. One site indicated that overall data quality was very good,

however variables such as symptom onset, exact swab date, and later, exact date of COVID-19 vaccination were difficult to collect. Data quality of one site improved after specific improvement initiatives, however was impacted by frequent changes of the surveillance and testing strategies, and prioritisation of GPs of roll-out of the COVID-19 vaccination programmes. One site noted that training the GP network helped to increase completeness of variables, particularly regarding dates of symptom onset and vaccination. For this site, vaccination register data was linked in the second year, which eliminated the missing data issues altogether.

Barriers for data quality for instance were not getting access to all variables needed, particularly in the first year. When these variables became available for one site in the second year through data linkage, not all cases were initially identified for surveillance and sentinel sites had to provide these cases retrospectively. The data validation process therefore was tedious. One site stated that completeness and validity of data collected by surveys varied according to the questions asked. Another site mentioned variation between regions in data collection possibilities and readiness to start surveillance impacted on data completeness in the first year. Date of symptom onset was indicated as difficult to collect by three study sites. In the second year, data quality improved and sequencing of variants became possible. Collating the data of the regions, data checking and validating for a national level dataset was a time-consuming process throughout the project. Difficulties with interpretation of real-time PCR-test data was noted by one site. Although data linkage solved a number of missing data issues, lacking a personal identification number inhibited linkage to registry data.

3.5.2 Timeliness

The performance of the surveillance regarding timeliness includes the speed between the steps in a surveillance system, from even occurrence, recognition, report, to control and prevention activities. Although I-MOVE-COVID-19 was not set up for reporting pooled surveillance data monthly, the project team was able to receive monthly data. However, the evolution of the SARS-CoV-2 virus was much faster than was envisaged at the outset of the project, when the outbreak was not yet declared a pandemic, and overwhelmed the health systems of the study sites. To relieve sites from the enormous workload, additional to national obligations and their regular work, data extracts were changed to bimonthly intervals. Timeliness for surveillance purposes with the pooled data was therefore limited; for research the frequency of data extracts was timely enough. Another challenge was to obtain timely sequencing data.

The study sites generally rated the timeliness of the data as good in the first year, reflected in a rating of four or five points by six sites, three sites site rated three points, one site two points. For the second year, the self-rates of the two and three pointers improved to four points except for one site. Sites reported that data was timelier than they were used to with influenza surveillance. Timeliness however varied for different types of data, and was impacted by changed patient pathways. According to one site, complete data consolidation from syndromic surveillance took up to three weeks in the first year. One site reported that epidemiological and clinical data were very fast, whereas there was lag time with reporting lab test data, and with vaccination data after first roll-out of the immunization programme. In the second year the latter improved substantially. Another site noted improvements in timeliness in the second year as well, by getting access to data in real time through a dedicated platform. Lag time for sequencing data was mentioned by one site.

3.5.3 Representativeness

The representativeness of a surveillance system is the ability to accurately describe the occurrence of an event of time, place, and person. On the project level, pooling data for surveillance purposes was challenging due to the substantial differences in number of cases reported by each of the study sites. Depending on the surveillance system in use, either sentinel or population-based after adaptations for COVID-19 surveillance, the sites bimonthly provided data ranging from thousands of cases to less than ten cases. For research purposes the between country variation of sample sizes was not problematic. For surveillance the data were weighted to account for these differences.

On the country level, the changed patient pathways and the availability of online booking/walk-in community testing centres in some of the countries raised questions about representativeness of the patients attending the GP, resulting in a biased selection of patients. Other sites used data from universal surveillance, including all cases. In the first phase of the pandemic, criteria for testing eligibility varied across countries, for instance with regard to symptoms, age-group, and priority groups such as healthcare workers. When immunisation programmes were rolled-out, most sites were able to provide data about target groups for vaccination and a timeline for eligibility for vaccination by target group. Providing representative sequencing information appeared to be challenging, for instance due to high cycle threshold values and low viral load in swabs.

Two sites rated the representativeness of their surveillance in the first year as excellent, five sites rated three points, one site rated two points, and one site rated representativeness as poor. In the second year three sites changed their rating, improving from two to three points and from three to four points respectively, and one site degraded from three points to one point. For one sentinel system practitioners were recruited to arrive at a nationally representative sample, that had even better coverage in the second year. One site had a surveillance system in place that covered the entire community level, including both public and private settings.

The sites that had the largest changes in patient pathway reported that their samples were largely affected by alternative testing routes and healthcare seeking behaviour, resulting in a biased selection of patients sampled in sentinel surveillance (for instance regarding specific age groups). Three sites mentioned regional underrepresentation, due to either gaps in coverage in certain areas, to differences in engagement of individual sentinel sites, or due to inability of certain regions to participate in the surveillance system. One site indicated that there may be bias in GPs more often reporting COVID-19 positive cases than negative cases. One site mentioned that it was difficult to define denominators and determine re-infections or multiple ARI episodes in one patient.

3.5.4 Simplicity

The simplicity of a surveillance system entails the system's structure and ease of operation. As discussed before, the I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care surveillance data collection protocol allowed study sites to provide data in formats and coding of their preference. A number of study sites initially experienced difficulties with ethical clearance for data sharing for the project, which hampered data provision in the first phase of the project. In autumn 2020, all sites obtained clearance and provided data. To foster simplicity and reduce workload for GPs, a number of study sites proposed to keep data collection for COVID-19 surveillance as similar as possible to influenza surveillance and added only a limited set of COVID-19 specific variables to their data collection.

The majority of the study sites (five) rated the simplicity of their surveillance system as good or excellent (4 or 5 points). Three sites rated three points, one site rated two points in the first year and improved to three points in the second year. One site noted that, once the influenza surveillance system was majorly adapted for COVID-19 surveillance, computer tools used within the system facilitated simplicity. The system of another site in itself is fairly easy in its operation, however posed high workload on participating GPs in an already busy time. One site indicated that collection of particularly date related variables (such as symptom onset date) was challenging for GPs. One site reported that data collection and reporting was simple due to the use of secondary data and linkage. The downside nevertheless was in the high workload for data validation, which was mentioned by another study site as well. One site reported that the use of an online platform for sharing standardised data from different regions simplified transfer and pooling of data at national level. Minimising the actors involved in the process facilitates ease of the surveillance system.

Obtaining permissions for data sharing was mentioned by one site as difficult, and temporary easing of sharing for the pandemic was withdrawn in the second pandemic year. Another site that rated simplicity of their system two points in the first year (three points in the second year), evaluated their system as complex. To integrate the established GP sentinel system into a newly established COVID-19 testing centres took quite some time, while involving multiple (partly new) stakeholders added to the complexity of the system. In the second year the processes were more streamlined.

3.5.5 Flexibility

The surveillance system's flexibility involves the ability to adapt to changing information needs or technical operating conditions. As discussed before, the countries very rapidly adapted their influenza surveillance systems, or established new systems, to monitor COVID-19. Although not all the study sites were able to deliver data from the outset of the study, they all, almost instantly, had a system operational for national surveillance. Data sharing issues initially hampered a number of study sites in flexibility to adapt to data sharing for the project. With regard to data collection, the flexibility to include additional variables was indicated to be limited in autumn 2020, particularly to relieve GPs from high workload. Data linkage enabled some study sites to collect additional variables.

Seven study sites rated the flexibility of their surveillance system with a four or five, two sites rated three points (one of these sites rated four points for the second year). Most sites indicated that they were able to respond quickly to changing information needs, such as collecting new variables, and linkage to other data sources. One site mentioned that they were able to increase reporting frequency rather swiftly and started direct patient and serology sampling. Another site indicated that their system was adapted at various times throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. One of the sites responded that changing the case definition is not easy and required re-training of GPs, however in an emergency situation (as was the pandemic) these adaptations were achieved quickly.

Using secondary epidemiological and clinical data, by one of the sites, challenged the possibilities to include new variables. One site indicated that the system in itself was flexible, nevertheless it takes time to adapt to including new pathogens for virological testing. It particularly takes time to adapt the laboratory information system to include new variables collected through the swabbing collection form. Another study site responded that the lack of a baseline surveillance system that was able to process large numbers of cases hampered flexibility of the system. In the second year, the use of computer tools however largely increased the system's flexibility.

3.5.6 Acceptability

The surveillance system's acceptability refers to the willingness of persons and organisations to participate in the system. Particularly in established systems, engagement of healthcare professionals and also political engagement was indicated by the study sites as strength for the system's performance. To enable full reflection on the system's acceptability, participating healthcare workers, patients, and other involved stakeholders should be included. The systems' acceptability therefore reflects merely the view of the study sites' representatives.

The sites varied in the rating of their system's acceptability. One site rated five points, three sites rated four points, three sites three points, and one site two points. Whereas three sites indicated that acceptability has increased in the second year (one site from three to four points, two sites from two to four points), two sites saw acceptability declining (reflected in the rating dropping from four to three points, or from four points to one point). One site reported an excellent degree of acceptability of the people responsible for the system and good synergy between the health organisations of the region. According to another site, the sentinel surveillance interfered with the aims of the national testing strategy to rapidly detecting and isolating all SARS-CoV-2 infections. To avoid competition with the national testing strategy and increase acceptability of virological surveillance, virological surveillance in the second year was changed to collecting saliva samples instead of nasopharyngeal swabs. Recognition of the importance of sentinel surveillance, ease of implementation, and linkage of health registries were pivotal factors for acceptance.

Whereas engagement of GPs for some study sites was large in the first year, other sites indicated that acceptance increased in the second year. Changed patient pathways (to community testing centres) were indicated as either hampering acceptance due to small number of eligible patients for testing, or as facilitator due to stability and ease of implementing testing. The high workload for GPs was mentioned by three sites as barriers for acceptability of the system. Co-existence of universal and sentinel surveillance was another barrier for both willingness and ability to participate in the latter system. One site indicated that the added value of having a sentinel system was questioned when having universal surveillance operational.

3.5.7 Stability

The stability of a surveillance system entails the system's reliability (ability to collect, manage, and provide data without failure) and availability (ability to be operational when needed). As discussed before, all study sites were able to provide data from the end of 2020 onwards. Initially some sites experienced shortages in materials for testing, such as test kits and personal protective materials, which challenged the ability to collect data. Some sites provided data in different formats with each data extract. Considering the changes in patient pathways and variation in system adaptations, the ability to collect data may be different from the ability to provide data. That notion was reflected in the study site's responses.

Five sites evaluated their surveillance systems as stable, with either four or five points throughout the two study years. One site indicated that their perceived stability improved from three points in the first year to five points in the second year. In the first year the system was stretched due to new participating practices and data sources. In the second year, efforts to migrate the curated variables to standardised formats resulted in much more stability. One site was particularly positive about their system's stability and indicated that absolute availability, exhaustive review of data, and

reinforcement of surveillance by medical public health guards contributed to stability of the system. A well-established system was mentioned by a study site as contributor to stability as well, although change of patient pathway inhibited continuous data collection. Disruption of the sentinel system due to changing patient pathways was mentioned by two other study sites as well. One site responded that data collection was predominantly stable throughout the project, however was affected by a decreasing number of participating health centres from the fourth quarter of 2021 resulting from again changing pathways for respiratory patients. In addition, at that time health professionals perceived epidemiological data less useful since contact tracing was not mandatory for all cases. One site indicated that although the same surveillance system was used throughout the pandemic, the multiple changes to the data collection forms may have made data collection cumbersome for GPs and required simplifications at some time.

Due to overwhelming of the system at the outset of the Omicron-variant surge, one study site found some of the regions aborting their participation in surveillance. That did not affect the stability of the system too much, since these regions were replaced by other regions. In addition, one site indicated that Omicron increased the clinical demands on GPs and demand on the laboratory capacity, which in turn impacted virological data availability.

3.5.8 Sustainability

The surveillance system's sustainability refers to the ongoing maintenance and support of a routine epidemiological and/or virological surveillance system. Six study sites rated the sustainability of their surveillance systems with four or five points, three sites rated three points. Systems that were majorly adapted for COVID-19 surveillance face new challenges in the phase of scaling down community testing facilities. To enable COVID-19 surveillance parallel to surveillance of other respiratory pathogens, some systems need to be reconfigured again. One site indicated that the epidemiological and virological surveillance was reinforced by the pandemic. Similarly, another site reported that surveillance was prioritised and now needs to be consolidated. Alternatively, two sites noticed that the pandemic yielded activities and dedication of staff for which their viability on the long-term is uncertain. As one site described, the heavy workload for GPs may have been acceptable during the pandemic, however is not sustainable in regular times. Two study sites referred to government agreements for sustainability of the system, one of which these are in place, and one site for which sustainability was depending on government funding. Long establishment of the system, with settled routines and dedicated staff, was mentioned by another site.

3.6 Reflections on participation in the consortium and SWOT analysis

Throughout the project, the primary care surveillance teams reflected on their tasks in the project during project meetings, bilateral meetings between study sites and the project coordination team, and email conversations. In the survey to the study sites, representatives of the sites reflected on the whole project. Study site focal points were additionally asked to conduct a SWOT analysis, considering the **S**trengths, **W**eaknesses, **O**pportunities, and **T**hreats from primary care surveillance for the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project. These entail both features of individual study sites and high-level project characteristics, as these were often difficult to disentangle and study site specific issues impacted on the project as well.

3.6.1 Participation in the consortium

Given the challenges of changed patient pathways and disrupted sentinel surveillance systems, and despite the considerable differences between study sites in surveillance systems and data collection, participating in the I-MOVE-COVID-19 consortium was generally valued by the study sites. At national level, participating in the consortium yielded leverage in meeting national surveillance objectives, was mentioned to be part of the motivation to have national surveillance in place, highlighted the importance to strengthen and expand the sentinel surveillance, provided an opportunity to pilot an ARI sentinel surveillance system, and contributed to improvement of quality of information. In addition, as one site reflected, participation in the consortium likely influenced national (government) support and funding. Two study sites flagged the added value for their country of using the pooled results for risk factor and VE studies, which was not possible at national level due to limited numbers of cases. Another site appreciated comparison with 'colleagues' approaches.

The study sites indicated that data collection according to the protocol, adapted to the country specific situation, was feasible but challenging. Particularly the extensive set of variables that had to be collected, data management and validation, and burden for health professionals were mentioned as barriers. A number of sites indicated that they appreciated support from the project coordination team with data validation and adapting protocols.

3.6.2 Strengths

The strengths of the project refer to the internal project organisation and may reflect what went well in the project, the added value compared with other studies, and knowledge and resources that were unique to this project.

On the study site level, a particular strength to enable adaptation of primary care sentinel surveillance for ILI to COVID-19 was the presence of (voluntary) long-established systems and networks between GPs, labs and public health professionals. That enables integration of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance in the existing influenza and other respiratory surveillance. Flexibility and adaptability were mentioned as strength as well. Political engagement and commitment of staff for enabling efforts to maintain sentinel surveillance systems, and having (human) resources dedicated for both programme management and clinical advice were noted as key drivers as well. Study sites updated database dictionaries, and completed vaccination calendars to align data with eligibility of target groups for COVID-19 vaccination.

On the project level, the long established I-MOVE team was valued for its experience, familiarity, friendliness, coordination, and good project members. The areas of focus and investigation were well chosen, according to one of the study sites. International collaboration, learning from each other's experiences and allowing to have space for sharing experiences between countries and study sites to discuss the protocol, its implementation, and data results were considered strengths as well.

3.6.3 Weaknesses

The weaknesses of the project entail the internal project organisation and reflect what needed to be improved and what knowledge and resources were lacking.

The sharp increase in GP practices resulted in challenges in terms of data quality in one site. Data collection was challenging in three other sites as well, for example clinicians perceived data collection as time-consuming and tedious due to the many variables to collect in mandatory systems, that were

not user-friendly. Two sites faced challenges with the logistics of transportation of samples. For instance, transportation of samples from remote and rural areas resulted in delayed testing processes. In one of these countries, initially multiple modes of transport were used. Later, testing was decentralised, helping speed up swab processing and sharing of results. Shortages in personal protective equipment, swabs, reagents or extraction kits for swab processing were noted by multiple sites in the first phase of the pandemic. One site therefore aborted testing for other respiratory pathogens due to constraints in laboratory capacity. Lack of (dedicated) staff and other resources were mentioned as weakness as well. One study site considered, besides lack of resources, lack of time, with other priority work during the pandemic, and lack of IT-infrastructure, impeded access to vaccination data and limited data linkage options were weaknesses.

On the project level, perceived weaknesses were differences between European bodies in their health systems and differences in data variables collected. The extensive set of variables that should be collected, resulting in large numbers of questions to health professionals and coinciding workload challenged completeness of data. Although providing weekly information was not an objective of this study, one site reflected on timeliness of the data provided as weakness and point of improvement and advantage to contribute to early detection. Improvement was observed to be needed in integrating clinical and virological (sequencing) data. The many unknowns at the outset of the project, such as range of disease symptoms, were perceived as weakness.

3.6.4 Opportunities

External to the project organisation and beyond its direct control were opportunities that the project advantaged and unanticipated information needs that the project met.

According to one of the study sites, the pandemic in itself provided a good opportunity to improve previous surveillance systems and emphasised the importance of having such systems in place. Moreover, engagement with new stakeholders has facilitated development of the surveillance system and will facilitate future development. The project yielded lessons about implementation and sustainability of sentinel networks during a pandemic that are useful to prepare for future pandemics. In addition, as was indicated by another site, an opportunity was to showcase sentinel surveillance for emergency preparedness. The substantial financial support from the EC for studies as I-MOVE-COVID-19 was considered as opportunity as well. The project itself was viewed as opportunity for future collaborative studies.

3.6.5 Threats

External to the project organisation and out of its direct control were threats that disadvantaged the project and for which the project was unprepared for.

The threats that were observed predominantly included the change of patient referral/testing pathways due to changing testing policies and subsequent changes to health seeking behaviour, resulting in diminishing of samples taken or retrieving samples from testing centres. For instance, in one study site the reduction emerged from an increase of tele-consultations, yet in another site symptomatic patients were initially tested in dedicated COVID-19 practices and later on in testing centres. One site indicated that diagnostic tests initially were only available through the sentinel surveillance system, which increased GP participation and sample numbers. However, availability of tests through parallel testing routes later in the pandemic led to major declines in both the number of patients attending/consulting practices and the number of participating practices. The availability

or lack of resources and sufficiently experienced and trained staff threatened surveillance. In addition, the emergence of the Omicron-variant impacted the whole surveillance system in December 2021 and January 2022, including GP reporting, availability of lab test data, reporting, and data quality. For future surveillance, ceasing operation of COVID-19 testing centres and required reconfiguration of sentinel surveillance may be a threat to reporting. One study reported that there were different institutions at country and European level working on COVID-19 and ARI surveillance and sometimes their rules were conflicting. Uncertainty about the availability of ongoing or longer term project funding by the EC was perceived as threat.

3.7 Future preparedness of sentinel surveillance

Formal evaluation of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance was carried out continuously in one study site, one site indicated that evaluation was commenced for May 2022. One site mentioned that formal evaluation has not taken place yet, however anticipating on outcomes, respiratory surveillance is being expanded. Other sites indicated that no formal evaluation has been carried out. Nevertheless, from the experiences of the individual study sites and primary care surveillance within the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project, prerequisites for future preparedness of sentinel surveillance could be derived.

3.7.1 Lessons from the first pandemic phase (March 2020 – September 2020)

From the first pandemic phase and the rapid adaptations that were made to the surveillance systems, prerequisites for sustainability of surveillance could be condensed to preparedness, adaptability/flexibility, sorting out the data-infrastructure, and awareness of the dual purpose of testing for diagnostics and surveillance and its consequences. Preparedness includes having or making dedicated resources available, for instance for public health teams and coordination of surveillance, and being prepared for high caseload. Flexible systems are needed to adapt quickly to new routines, such as the use of self-swabbing, decentralisation of lab testing and the availability of telephone/video consultations. One of the sites indicated the importance of developing and establishing new protocols and readiness checklists in order to communicate to multiple stakeholders and support rapid implementation. The importance of data infrastructure was noted by three countries. Information systems need to be flexible, data duplication in both collecting and reporting should be avoided, data completeness should be prioritised and fed back to surveillance teams.

The dual purpose of testing and sentinel surveillance involved new partnerships with different stakeholders. One site noted the need to consider surveillance when making changes to patient pathways. Another site indicated that the contribution of sentinel GP surveillance to the national testing strategy during a pandemic is reconsidered, as their role was too small.

3.7.2 Looking forward

Considering the period from March 2020 to March 2022, study sites were asked to reflect on challenges for sustainability of sentinel surveillance and give recommendations to ensure preparedness of sentinel surveillance for future outbreaks or pandemic waves. We should also learn from other international comparisons; across the developed world there were similarly acceleration in digital maturity and development in disease surveillance (Kuziemy, 2022; Liaw, 2021; Tu, 2022).

Funding for human resources, and other resources such as IT, laboratory resources, and training are key factors in sustaining a sentinel surveillance system in primary care. Additionally, stakeholder engagement is pivotal, in particular with the participating GPs in the sentinel networks, in order to increase stability and representativeness of the networks. A related issue is the recruitment and retention of GPs in the network, which may be difficult due to the high workload and post-pandemic perceived lack of urgency. The latter may impact on public acceptance and patient participation as well. One site indicated that the acceptability of sentinel surveillance as the appropriate system to monitor other respiratory pathogens besides SARS-CoV-2 and influenza may be challenging sustainability of this surveillance.

To enhance preparedness for future outbreaks, representativeness of surveillance networks should be improved and syndromic surveillance should be strengthened. Data access should be improved for institutions that perform surveillance, for instance to registry data. Moreover, regional surveillance systems need to be consolidated and provide timely information to be prepared for future outbreaks. And surveillance systems should operate year-round, if not already. The impact on existing surveillance systems should be considered when testing policies are under review/change during epidemic or pandemic periods. Alternatively, sentinel surveillance may be embedded in the newly established response structure. Nevertheless, it should be kept in mind that sentinel surveillance is suitable for testing a systematic sample of patients and is not intended for large scale diagnostic testing of a notifiable disease.

At European level, continuity of teams and collaboration with other networks, such as in the I-MOVE-COVID-19 consortium, provides reassurance that surveillance systems are fit for purpose. By using such collaboration as platform on European level, procedures and challenges as well as good practices could be shared and surveillance methods could be harmonised.

4 Discussion

4.1 Summary of findings

The purpose of this final evaluation is to learn about the challenges participating sites faced during the adaptation of a primary care surveillance system to the pandemic progression. Primary care surveillance of the individual study sites and collaboration within the I-MOVE-COVID-19 consortium was evaluated using information collated during the project and a survey administered among study sites in the final phase of the project.

The COVID-19 pandemic resulted in widespread disruption to public health and healthcare systems across the world. In line with international guidelines, existing respiratory/influenza sentinel surveillance systems were adapted to incorporate COVID-19 surveillance. The extent of system adaptations was wide-ranging, varying from almost no changes to sentinel surveillance systems in two study sites, moderate changes in two other sites, the implementation of completely new systems in four countries and complete cessation/disruption of sentinel surveillance in two of these countries. The main issue for sentinel surveillance therefore was that data collection routines changed due to the aforementioned structure changes in primary care, resulting in new routes and routines in data streams. Moreover, health care seeking behaviour changed and affected data collection. For example, patients with respiratory symptoms went to general testing centres instead of consulting in-person at primary care centres.

Overall, all primary care study sites were able to meet national surveillance objectives, either through sentinel surveillance or using data from population-based testing for national surveillance. For primary care surveillance regarding the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project however, countries differed in the data they provided for the project. Countries that still had sentinel surveillance operational provided data from smaller numbers of cases than usual for influenza surveillance, due to the changed patient pathways and diminished numbers of patients with respiratory symptoms attending or consulting general practice. Countries that set up new surveillance systems or integrated population-based testing in primary care surveillance were able to provide data for the project. Nevertheless, the data flows reflected different samples than the original sentinel surveillance systems would have provided. The I-MOVE-COVID-19 pooled primary care surveillance was not planned for rapid detection of COVID-19 cases by practitioners, while on national or regional level there was an urgent need for this and was provided by other newly established COVID-19 surveillance systems.

The pooled primary care surveillance data enabled description of clinically diagnosed or laboratory confirmed cases by rapid antigen or PCR tests according to patient characteristics. Symptoms were well collected by all study sites. Underlying chronic disease and other risk factors, such as health behaviour were not feasible to collect for some study sites due to data linkage limitations or limitation of workload for health professionals. Sequencing was conducted, however for a limited number of samples and with substantial lag times. Cases were reported in a sufficiently timely manner to enable VE and risk factor studies, which was the main strength of pooled primary care surveillance. At the outset of the study, COVID-19 vaccination was not envisaged yet as part of this

surveillance project. Nevertheless, when immunisation programmes were rolled out in the participating countries, the bimonthly dataflow enabled rapid VE-studies.

Regarding the fitness for purpose and use of the surveillance systems, reflected in eight surveillance attributes, the primary care surveillance systems perceived their performance fairly well given the circumstances of changed patient pathways and limitations of data collection. The differences between study sites in the evaluation of their surveillance system were noticeable and were partly reflected in the evaluation of data quality. The completeness of the data was very good, when the required information could be collected within the surveillance system. However, due to adaptations of some of the sentinel surveillance systems, some previously collected data could no longer be collected.

Frequency of reporting was planned with intervals of 6 months and in the second year, of 12 months. During the course of the pandemic, a more frequent data collection and reporting was discussed with the partners. For instance, collecting aggregated weekly numbers of patients with COVID-19, consulting in primary care (GP visit or telephone consultation), stratified by age group, sex, and region/country. However, weekly aggregated surveillance was not feasible. Partly due to data collection that worked out differently than foreseen (alternative testing routes) and partly due to enormous workload of study sites.

International data sharing and ethical approval requirements proved difficult for some study sites and required a lengthy period of time to be resolved. However, a clear progression throughout the project was observed and the experiences we take as many lessons learnt for future practice.

4.2 Limitations

The evaluation of primary care surveillance was challenged by a number of limitations. One limitation is that the adaptations to and performance of the surveillance systems as reported in the surveys by representatives of the study sites reflect the perception of the participants. As they were subjected to enormous workload, they may have overlooked the full range of changes that were implemented in their sentinel surveillance system. It may have been challenging, if not impossible, to disentangle the objectives of surveillance in the wider sense of pandemic control, providing data for research studies (e.g. on risk factors), and attributes of surveillance system functioning. Secondly, the substantial differences between study sites in the configuration of primary care surveillance systems challenged generally applicable statements and recommendations. In addition, the evaluation is carried out from the perspectives of the study site focal points and project coordinating team. Perceptions of other stakeholders such as healthcare professionals, patients, and Ministries of Health were not included.

4.3 Strengths

A strength of this project, aiming at surveillance on EU-level is that it yielded a substantial and steady data flow for risk factor and VE studies. Data collection on national level was levered by the EU surveillance purpose. With funding of this project, national surveillance systems were bolstered as well. The project also yielded data linkage, resulting in very rich and valid data. Linking sequencing

data was progressed due to this project. Data collection for surveillance gave a lever to progress with data collection for VE and risk factor studies. The long history and experience of participating study sites in the underlying I-MOVE projects and good collaboration between partners were beneficial for the project, as standard procedures around data collection, extraction and processing were familiar to sites.

4.4 Recommendations

The COVID-19 pandemic put a lot of pressure on the primary care surveillance systems. Nevertheless, valuable lessons could be derived for the near future of the transition from large scale testing to sentinel surveillance. Moreover, this evaluation translates to a number of recommendations to prepare surveillance for future outbreaks or pandemics.

To foster sustainability of sentinel surveillance, the workload imposed by data collection and validation should be minimised as much as possible. Marbus et al. (21) propose that surveillance should serve dual goals, for both public health and patient care, and should be integrated in the regular healthcare process. More harmonisation of data standards, automatised data collection/extraction and validation, and support of data specialists may lower the administrative burden of sentinel surveillance. Furthermore, with novel respiratory viruses and subsequent reviewing or changing testing policies and patient pathways in healthcare systems, data/surveillance experts should be involved to align adequate data collection during planning stages. In addition, it is very likely there will be more and more point of care tests driven by antimicrobial stewardship and high cost treatments like monoclonals that need to be given early in disease. Self-testing is likely to remain. Flexibility of the surveillance system is pivotal to enable upscaling from sentinel surveillance to community testing data in case of surges.

In adapting existing primary care surveillance systems to monitoring new pathogens with epidemic of pandemic potential, it is pivotal to include database specialists to enable secondary use of healthcare (registry) data for surveillance purposes. On the other hand, in the transition from daily testing in walk-in COVID-19 testing centres to downscaling testing capacity in spring 2022, some countries could return to primary care sentinel surveillance as usual. Other countries will have to change the whole system back since the entire surveillance routine has changed.

4.5 Conclusions

The different objectives of I-MOVE-COVID-19, surveillance and research for vaccine effectiveness and risk factors, required different data handling routines. The surveillance objective demands timely country-specific data, whereas the research objective requires pooled data from study sites that needs to be carefully validated. For surveillance the validation process may have been more lenient than for the research component. However, to lower the workload for the study sites, data extraction was minimised to bimonthly and served both purposes of surveillance and research.

The huge workload that was imposed on both the study sites and the project coordination team due to the rapid evolution of the COVID-19 pandemic, overwhelming the countries health systems, was not envisaged at the outset of the study. Data collection therefore was pragmatic and study sites

provided data that was available, which sometimes deviated from the data specification according to the protocol and changed from the primary care setting to community-based. When a novel virus is emerging, it was proven to be difficult to balance all data that preferably should be collected with workload. Particularly at the outset it was challenging to determine what data was essential to capture key knowledge and answer research questions.

A strength of this European network has been its ability to be adaptive to changing circumstances even when this means diverting from its original objectives. Future plans for sentinel surveillance should recognise the requirements to be responsive in the way we have demonstrated across the COVID-19 pandemic.

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Annex 1: Changes to primary care influenza sentinel systems in response to the first phase of the COVID-19 pandemic

	Country*	Description of influenza sentinel system pre-COVID-19	Changes made in response to COVID-19			
			Participating sites; sampling criteria	Data collection	Testing process	Strengths/ Challenges/ Lessons
Minor/ no changes	Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 79 primary care practices (GPs and paediatric clinics) covering 6.4% of the population. - GP takes face to face swab - Doctors asked to swab the first 5 ARI/ ILI patients that enter the practice per week (around 50 samples per week) - Data collected by the GP during the consultation on paper and online. - Data validated by the Public Health Agency of Sweden - Samples transported by the public postal system. - Samples tested for influenza only at the Public Health Agency of Sweden. - Results shared through weekly reports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in registered sampling practices to 102 (coverage 7.9%) during the peak and reduction to 15 (coverage 1.5%) post-peak. - No change in who takes the swab. - No change in sampling strategy. All additional samples also tested. - Influenza surveillance stopped week 15 - Sweden started to offer testing for everyone in June 2020 which resulted in a decline in number of swabs taken by registered GPs. 	- No change	- No change	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Established sentinel system and protocols; reimbursement to registered GPs for first five samples. - Sentinel samples were used for diagnostic purposes which encouraged attendance prior to change in patient pathway. - Now using sentinel system to offer Influenza and COVID-19 testing. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low coverage in some counties. - Change in patient pathway reduced number of samples sent through GPs. - Reduction in capacity meant had to stop recruiting more GPs to register - Shortage of reagents <p>Lessons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be prepared for high caseload - Urgency creates flexibility - Difficult to obtain two swabs (diagnostic and sentinel surveillance)
	Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 40 registered ILI sentinel practices covering around 0.8% of population. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No change in sentinel surveillance strategy or registered practices. 	No change	No change	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Established integrated epidemiological and virological sentinel system and protocols;

	Country*	Description of influenza sentinel system pre-COVID-19	Changes made in response to COVID-19			
			Participating sites; sampling criteria	Data collection	Testing process	Strengths/ Challenges/ Lessons
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GPs test the first two ILI patients on Monday through Wednesday. If no patients attend GPs test the first two patients with ILI or ARI from Thursday to Sunday. At least one should be under 10 yrs. - Samples tested for influenza, RSV, rhinovirus, and enterovirus. - Data is collected on paper, face to face and entered by the laboratory into the RIVM Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS). - Samples are sent by regular mail and tested at the National Influenza Centre at the National Institute of Public Health and the Environment (RIVM). - Results are entered into the LIMS by the RIVM. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patient pathway changed and public was asked to stay at home if not severely unwell. GPs organised collaborative consultation offices for suspect patients. This reduced the case load and number of sentinel swabs as GPs can only submit swabs of their own patients. - In June post- peak testing centres have been set up further reducing the caseload. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reimbursement incentive to GPs depending on number of swabs taken. - Sentinel swabs are used for diagnostic purposes (although can take days) which encourages patients to have them swabbed. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in patient pathway reducing consultation numbers. - Testing for symptomatic patients was redirected to municipal health services, bypassing GPs. - GPs formed collaboratives which reduced the case load and number of sentinel swabs as GPs can only submit swabs of own patients. <p>Lessons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sentinel surveillance too limited to contribute to national testing strategy with rapid sample-to-result times of less than 48 hours, 7 days/week.
Modest changes	France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 333 sentinel GPs and paediatricians (0.3% coverage) at least. - GPs sample 1 ILI patient of any age and 2 elderly ARI patients. Paediatricians sample 1 ILI patient. Samples were face to face by consulting physician. - Patient information collected on paper by physician during consultation. Form sent to lab 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of participating sites stayed same during peak. Post peak Sentinelles surveillance stopped and testing transferred over to the National Testing Strategy. - During peak ILI syndromic surveillance replaced with ARI. GPs sampled 1 ARI patient <65 & 1 ARI patient 65+; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During peak pre-COVID-19 process followed for data collection. - Post peak data collected online by participating GP and transferred using secure app or dedicated website or over phone in some 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public mail + other mail service to transport samples - At peak NRCs tested. Post peak medical labs tested as per national testing strategy independent of Sentinelles surveillance. 	<p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disturbance in postal service - Lack of PPE - Increases in teleconsultations reducing number of samples - Cessation of pathogen testing due to lab capacity

	Country*	Description of influenza sentinel system pre-COVID-19	Changes made in response to COVID-19			
			Participating sites; sampling criteria	Data collection	Testing process	Strengths/ Challenges/ Lessons
		<p>and data entered onto database for secure transfer and storage to Sentinelles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Samples transported by public post. - Testing at 2 national reference centres (NRC) (CNR, Paris and Lyon) and at the University of Corsica. - Testing for influenza, hRV, VRS and hMPV. - Results sent to swabbing physician by email and available on Sentinelles account. 	<p>paediatricians sampled 1 ARI patient.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Post peak, generalised testing was made available from 18 May 2020. - Post peak, sentinelles GPs were allowed to retrospectively report on SARS-CoV-2 status by modification of electronic forms by adding a question on prescription of PCR test for SARS-CoV-2. 	<p>cases. Sentinelles epidemiologists verified all data cross checking with GP if needed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Post-peak labs stopped testing for some respiratory pathogens due to capacity but continued COVID-19 and Influenza until week 13. - Results sent electronically to SIDEPE (centralised COVID-19 results database), swabbing physician and patient. 	
	England	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 100 GP sentinel sites, 4-10 samples taken by the GP or practice nurse per practice per week. In addition UKHSA receives samples taken via drive through or face to face sampling through parallel testing channels set up across the UK. - Sampling of patients with ILI or LRTI; except those who opt out or had recent vaccination - Data collected on paper by GP practice. Some practices use automatically filled online form. Coded at practice and checked by RCGP RSC - Kit sent on request from RCGP RSC liaison team who request from UKHSA) supplier. - Samples tested centrally at Colindale, Respiratory Virus Unit. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During and after the peak number of sentinel sites increased to 300. 20 samples per week, more if needed. Goal, total 600 across all age bands. - During the peak sampling was offered to patients presenting with COVID-19 symptoms (within 7 days of onset), recent travel. Now patients presenting with ILI or LRTI or those suspected to have or have been exposed to COVID-19 with persistent cough/ loss of taste/ smell, SOB, fever or wheezing (within ten days of onset) - During the peak samples either taken face to face by GP, or self-swab (Drive through nationally provided). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Processes remain the same as pre COVID-19 - For samples collected through the drive through or parallel face to face testing sites, patient data is screened by GP practices and included in a centralised database overseen by UKHSA. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During the peak swabs taken in practice sent by post. Self-swabs sent by post (online voucher code piloted in 21 practices during the peak, this will be used by all from end September). - Testing location unchanged. - Samples only tested for COVID-19. - Results sent to the GP during the peak. Going forward results sent via e-Labs system and a text to those who self-swab. - Serology swabs go to the UKHSA centre in 	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong relationships and network. - University and RCGP support. - Adaptability in primary care. - Willingness to engage. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long time period from test to result. - Lack of PPE. Shortages in swabs. - Change in patient pathway meant patients not attending primary care. - Low remuneration. - No results flow for serology so patient doesn't get anything back. <p>Lessons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Importance of self-swabbing and its use. - Importance of links with labs to order tests and to share results directly with patients.

	Country*	Description of influenza sentinel system pre-COVID-19	Changes made in response to COVID-19			
			Participating sites; sampling criteria	Data collection	Testing process	Strengths/ Challenges/ Lessons
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test for influenza and other respiratory viruses. If negative tested further. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Also now doing serosurveillance of up to 1000 serology specimens per week. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manchester and sent to test sites. 	
Major changes	Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sentinel sites (GP and A&E) across the country, some regions underrepresented. 40,000 people covered. - Swabbing of all ILI patients. Around 1000 samples each season (wks 40 to 20). - Face to face swabs by GP or nurses. - Paper based data collection by attending physician. - Validation by network coordinators with verification by GP. - Samples transported by courier via the National Institute of Health (NIH). - Test for influenza and other respiratory pathogens if negative. - Results sent to GP or A&E focal point. Results available weekly on influenza surveillance report. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initially patients called national helpline for referral to reference health centre hospital (depending on clinical criteria) for swab following validation by medical Dr. Later tests at COVID-19 centres (drive through, private labs, health centres and hospitals) - All suspect cases meeting ECDC case definition tested. During peak also tested high risk contacts, exposed populations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data entered online by medical doctor. - Data collected face to face or over the phone. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initially testing centralised at National Reference Laboratory (NRL). Later SARS-CoV-2 testing was decentralised to public and private labs. - Testing for Influenza and other respiratory pathogens was not performed by all testing laboratories. - Dedicated transport of samples. - SARS-CoV-2 results notified through mandatory surveillance system. 	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong GP, lab and public health network with standard protocols. High voluntary participation. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Voluntary sentinel network made recruitment in some regions difficult. - Lack of resource for coordination - Medical records not available increasing burden of data collection in sentinel sites. - Mandatory surveillance system not user friendly with many variables which led to reduction in data quality. - Many information systems making communication challenging between levels. <p>Lessons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dedicated resource for coordination - If changing case management always consider surveillance. <p>Avoid duplication of data decentralisation of telephone lines and reference centres.</p>
	Scotland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 40 sentinel influenza GP practices covering around 6% of the population - Face to face swabs by the GP - Up to five samples per week between weeks 40 to 20. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patients called NHS24 (telephone help line). If case definition met, transferred to COVID-19 Hub (CH) for telephone consultation only (if mild symptoms) or further 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Paper based data collection by clinicians and some patients if self-swabbing. - Data sent by email to central team for entry. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Range of transport routes including royal mail, courier (bike, boat and air) - testing decentralised to private and public 	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong political buy in. - Proactive communication with key front line staff. - Clear protocols and readiness checklists.

	Country*	Description of influenza sentinel system pre-COVID-19	Changes made in response to COVID-19			
			Participating sites; sampling criteria	Data collection	Testing process	Strengths/ Challenges/ Lessons
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sampling of those with ILI at clinician discretion up to five per week, two under 14 yrs one 15-44 yrs and two 45 and over. - Data is collected by the GP or practice nurse on paper and emailed to the Flu team. - Validation by analysts on entry. - Samples transported by public mail services. - Testing at the West of Scotland Reference laboratory run by the NHS. - Tests for Influenza and other common respiratory pathogens using multiplex PCR. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - triaged to attend COVID-19 Assessment Centre (CAC) for face to face assessment (moderate symptoms). - Either self swab (CH), drive through (CH or CAC) or face to face (CAC). - CH and CACs asked to collect 500 swabs each, per week. Target set per health board according to population size. Initial effort to age stratify were stopped due to small sample size and change in testing policy where all had to be tested if presenting at a CAC. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data analysts match surveillance survey data to results and other variables. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - local labs via Health Boards - testing for COVID-19 only - Data sent to centralised results lab system (Electronic Communication of Surveillance in Scotland (ECOSS)). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dedicated human resource for programme management and clinical advice. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rapid change in patient pathway. Transportation of samples from remote rural areas. - Clinician completing data surveillance form extends consultation time. <p>Lessons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralise lab testing of samples to speed results back to patients - Flexibility to adapt to political context and changing patient pathways. - Prioritise data completeness feeding back to teams from the start. - Importance of dedicated personnel in the national and local teams.
	Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 772 sentinel GP (555) and paediatric practices (217) from 16 regional networks out of 19 regions covering 2.44% of the population. - First two patients attending for face to face consult who meet ILI definition. - Data collected by physician face to face on paper or electronic form depending on region. - Validation by national and regional coordinators and GPs. - Samples transported by courier via the regional influenza reference laboratories. A 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All COVID-19 cases were reported to the National Epidemiological Surveillance Network (RENAVE). - Testing strategy was changed depending on epidemiology. Initially testing of all suspect cases and then testing only of severe cases and health workers or other essential groups. - Testing depends on region with some regions using primary care network and others using COVID-19 testing centres. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data collected either on paper or electronically depending on the region. - Data transferred to the RENAVE through web platform (SiViES). - Information collected by public health or other health care professionals, by phone or through face to face interviews. - Validation as before. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initially testing centralised at the National Influenza Reference Centre. Later decentralised to public regional laboratories. - Only testing for COVID-19. - Dedicated transport of samples. - Mandatory notification to RENAVE. - Data sent to centralised Spanish 	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Well established system for inter-regional coordination and management of public health alerts and emergencies - Strong commitment of public health staff despite workload. - Flexibility to change from decentralised system to a centralised decision making system following declaration of the State of Alarm. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sentinel networks disrupted in all regions. - GPs relocated. - Lack of supplies including PPE.

	Country*	Description of influenza sentinel system pre-COVID-19	Changes made in response to COVID-19			
			Participating sites; sampling criteria	Data collection	Testing process	Strengths/ Challenges/ Lessons
		<p>selection of samples are sent to the National Influenza Reference Center for genetic/antigenic characterisation and B lineage determination.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results sent back to physicians and regional sentinel network coordination who share nationally with National Centre of Epidemiology ISCIH via online web platform. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Swabs taken by GPs or clinical staff in testing centre. 		Surveillance Information System (SiViES)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in patient pathways (telemedicine and parallel testing units) and health seeking behaviour. - Heavy data reporting requirements at national level caused delays in notification and a decrease in data quality. - Lack of dedicated personnel and IT resource at regional and national level. <p>Lessons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Importance of strong and flexible information system and IT structure. - Importance of dedicated public health network and adequate HR. - Avoid duplication of data reporting.

* Ireland was not included in this survey at the time due to disruption of the sentinel surveillance system.

Annex 2: Variables primary care surveillance dataset

Variable name	Description	Values and coding	Requested according to protocol, optional or derived variable	Delivered by study sites (N)	Used for reporting
Study identifiers					
id	Unique and persistent identifier for each record	[needs to be unique]	requested	7	yes
idcountry	Unique identified or country - is a 2-digit country code	2-digit country code	requested	9	yes
gpcode	Code for GP or healthcare center		optional	8	no
Patient demographics					
age	Age of participant in years	0, 1, 2, etc.	requested	7	no
agegp5	5 year age bands	0 = 0-4 years 1 = 4-9 years 2 = 10-14 years etc. 16 = 80-84 years 17 = 85+ years	requested, if age in years is not possible	9	yes
sex	Sex of study participant	0 = female 1 = male	requested	9	yes
region	Geographic region	Text	optional	4	no
Risk factors					
hcw	Patient is a healthcare worker	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	3	yes
smoking	Never, former (stopped smoking at least 1 year before inclusion in the study), current smoker. Any smoking can be included: cigarettes, cigars, vaping, etc.	0 = Never 1 = Former 2 = Current 9 = Do not know	requested	5	yes
pregnant	Pregnancy status	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	6	yes
travel	Travelled in the past 14 days?	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	2	yes
travel_country	Country of travel	Text	requested	2	yes
Pre-existing (chronic) conditions					
bmi ¹	Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)		requested	1	no

¹ If possible, we suggested to collect either BMI as a continuous variable (bmi variable) OR height and weight. If none of these were possible then we suggested to use the categorical variable "obese".

Variable name	Description	Values and coding	Requested according to protocol, optional or derived variable	Delivered by study sites (N)	Used for reporting
height	Height in cm		requested	1	no
weight	Weight in kg		requested	1	no
obese	If BMI or height and weight are not collected	0 = No (BMI <30) 1 = BMI ≥30-39 2 = BMI ≥40 8 = Do not know	requested, if BMI was not available	2	no
obese1	Obesity >= 30	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested, if BMI was not available	8	yes
diabetes	Diabetes and endocrine disease	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	9	yes
immuno	Immunodeficiency (disease OR therapy) and organ transplant; note: not well collected for PT	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	9	yes
immunosup_dis	Immunosuppressive disease	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	2	no
immunosup_ther	Taking immunosuppressive therapy	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	2	no
lungdis	Lung disease	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	9	yes
asthma	Asthma	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	5	yes
lungdis_noasth	Chronic lung disease without asthma	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	2	no
cancer	Cancer	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	5	yes
heart_dis	Heart disease	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	9	yes
heart_disnohyp	Heart disease without hypertension	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	3	no
hypertension	Hypertension	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	3	yes
hemato_dis	Chronic hematologic disease	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	1	yes
renal_dis	Renal disease	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	8	yes

Variable name	Description	Values and coding	Requested according to protocol, optional or derived variable	Delivered by study sites (N)	Used for reporting
liver_dis	Liver disease	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	8	yes
livren_disease	Liver or renal disease	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	8	yes
neuro_dis	Chronic neurological disorder	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	3	yes
rheum_dis	Rheumatological disease	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	2	yes
chronother	Other chronic condition	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	3	yes
chronother1	Yes/no for other chronic conditions that are in the protocol, outside of lung disease (incl or not asthma), heart disease (incl or not hypertension), immuno (incl therapy + disease), diabetes, pregnancy and obesity.	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	derived	8	yes
anychron	Yes/no for any of the chronic conditions as collected by the country.	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	derived	9	yes
anychron1	Yes/no for any of common chronic conditions: lung disease (incl or not asthma), heart disease (incl or not hypertension), immuno (incl therapy + disease), diabetes)	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	derived	9	yes
Vaccinations					
fluvaccany	Received flu vaccination in current season regardless of vaccination date	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	9	yes
fluvaccdate	Date of the most recent seasonal influenza vaccination	dd/mm/yyyy	optional		no
pneumovacc	Received pneumococcal vaccination	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	2	yes
pneumoyear	Year of latest pneumococcal vaccination	yyyy	optional	0	no

Variable name	Description	Values and coding	Requested according to protocol, optional or derived variable	Delivered by study sites (N)	Used for reporting
covvaccany	Any COVID-19 vaccination	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	9	yes
covvaccdoses	Total number of COVID-vaccinations	0, 1, 2, etc.	optional	9	no
covtarget	Belongs to target group COVID-19 vaccination at time of swabbing	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	9	yes
covvaccany_booster	Received any COVID-19 vaccine booster	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	9	no
covtarget_booster	Part of target group for booster	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	9	no
Clinical signs and symptoms					
onsetdate	Date of onset of symptoms	dd/mm/yyyy	requested	8	no
fever	Fever	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	6	yes
malaise	Malaise	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	5	yes
myalgia	Myalgia	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	5	yes
cough	Cough	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	6	yes
sorethroat	Sore throat	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	6	yes
suddenonset	Sudden onset	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	6	yes
headache	Headache	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	6	yes
shortness_of_breath	Shortness of breath	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	6	yes
anosmia	Anosmia (loss of sense of smell)	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	2	no
ageusia	Aguesia/disguesia (loss or distortion of sense of taste)	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	2	no
anosmia_ageusia	Has loss of sense of smell/taste	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	7	yes

Variable name	Description	Values and coding	Requested according to protocol, optional or derived variable	Delivered by study sites (N)	Used for reporting
fatigue	Fatigue	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	3	yes
coryza	Coryza	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	3	yes
chestpain	Chest pain	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	3	no
chills	Chills/feverishness	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	1	no
nausea	Nausea	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	1	no
vomiting	Vomiting	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	4	yes
diarrhoea	Diarrhoea	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	5	yes
vom_diar	Vomiting or diarrhoea	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	1	no
stomachache	Stomach ache	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	2	no
rash_derm	Rash or other dermatological manifestation	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	0	no
conjunctivitis	Conjunctivitis	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	2	no
dizziness	Dizziness	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	0	no
palpitations	Palpitations	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	1	no
confusion	Confusion	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	1	no
sputum	Sputum	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	1	no
pulm_auscult	Normal pulmonary auscultation	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	1	no
sneezing	Sneezing	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	optional	1	no

Variable name	Description	Values and coding	Requested according to protocol, optional or derived variable	Delivered by study sites (N)	Used for reporting
Diagnosis					
ili	Meets ILI case definition	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	6	yes
ari	Meets ARI case definition	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	9	yes
Severe outcome					
hosp_refer	Referral of patient to hospital for COVID-19	0 = No 1 = Yes 8 = Do not know	requested	2	yes
Information on swabbing					
consult_type	Type of consultation	0 = teleconsultation 1 = face to face 8 = do not know	requested	1	no
swabdate	Swabbing date	dd/mm/yyyy	requested	9	yes
swabdelay	Days between onset of symptoms and swabbing		derived	8	yes
swab_type	Type of swab taken for SARS-CoV-2	1 = Nose 2 = Throat 3 = Both nose and throat 8 = Do not know		1	no
swab_place	Where swabbing took place	1 = GP practice 2 = At home	optional	0	no
Laboratory results					
test_type	Type of test used for SARS-CoV-2 (if other, please specify)	1 = PCR 2 = Point of care 3 = Other 8 = Do not know	optional	7	yes
lab_sarscov2 (renamed case_cov)	Laboratory result for SARS-CoV-2 (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Inconclusive 8 = Do not know	requested	9	yes
lab_flu	Laboratory result for influenza (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Not done 8 = Do not know	optional	7	yes
lab_rsv	Laboratory result for RSV (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Not done 8 = Do not know	optional	2	yes
lab_metapneum	Laboratory result for human metapneumovirus (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Not done 8 = Do not know	optional	1	no

Variable name	Description	Values and coding	Requested according to protocol, optional or derived variable	Delivered by study sites (N)	Used for reporting
lab_rhinovirus	Laboratory result for rhinovirus (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Not done 8 = Do not know	optional	1	yes
lab_adenovirus	Laboratory result for adenovirus (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Not done 8 = Do not know	optional	0	no
lab_bocavirus	Laboratory result for bocavirus (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Not done 8 = Do not know	optional	0	no
lab_seascorona	Laboratory result for seasonal coronavirus (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Not done 8 = Do not know	optional	2	no
lab_enterovirus	Laboratory result for enterovirus (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Not done 8 = Do not know	optional	1	yes
lab_parainfluenza	Laboratory result for parainfluenza (positive/negative)	0 = Negative 1 = Positive 2 = Not done 8 = Do not know	optional	1	no

Annex 3: Survey study sites

European Union

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Survey for the evaluation of the I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care/outpatient surveillance

Dear I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care team,

One of the tasks under the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project entailed evaluating the participating surveillance systems at the primary care level in order to provide recommendations on how to adapt / set up a surveillance system to rapidly support surveillance in case of a public health emergency. With this questionnaire, we would gladly gather your experiences and reflections during the I-MOVE-COVID 19 project regarding primary care SARS-CoV-2 surveillance.

We would kindly ask to return one questionnaire per study site. Please return the questionnaire Friday 15 April 2022 at the latest.

Please note that reporting of the findings will be on high level and does not disclose any study site specific details.

If you would like to provide additional clarification and discuss experiences regarding primary care surveillance in the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project with other study sites, we will organize a group discussion on Wednesday 13 April, from 10:00 to 11:00 hours CEST. Would you please indicate at the end of the questionnaire if you would be interested to attend an additional group discussion? We will organise the group meeting only if at least two study sites would like to share their experiences more in-depth. Please do not feel the obligation to attend.

If you have any questions, do not hesitate to contact Tessa Jansen at t.jansen@nivel.nl.

We are very thankful for your input!

All the best,

I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care coordination team

Please note that the size of the free text boxes is amendable to the length of your answer.

1. Attributes of SARS-CoV-2 primary care/outpatient surveillance of your site

If you consider the attributes of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance listed below, could you give a rating of the performance of the primary care/outpatient surveillance (that provided data to I-MOVE-COVID-19) of your site?

- Please evaluate the surveillance systems' performance both in the first year of the project (March 2020 – March 2021) and in the second year of the project (March 2021 – March 2022).
- In addition, could you reflect on this rating? You may also reflect on changes between the years.

1.1 On a scale from 1 to 5 (5 being excellent), how would you rate the surveillance systems' performance with regard to data quality? Please mark the appropriate box with an X.

Could you briefly describe why this rating reflects the performance of the surveillance with regard to data quality?

Data quality: the completeness and validity of the data recorded in the surveillance system, including the addition of virological diagnostics.

First year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						
Second year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						

3.1 On a scale from 1 to 5 (5 being excellent), how would you rate the surveillance systems' performance with regard to timeliness? Please mark the appropriate box with an X.

Could you briefly describe why this rating reflects the performance of the surveillance with regard to timeliness?

Timeliness: the speed between steps in a surveillance system, from event occurrence, recognition, report, to control and prevention activities.

First year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						
Second year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						

3.2 On a scale from 1 to 5 (5 being excellent), how would you rate the surveillance systems' performance with regard to representativeness? Please mark the appropriate box with an X.

Could you briefly describe why this rating reflects the performance of the surveillance with regard to representativeness?

Representativeness: the ability to accurately describe the occurrence of an event over time, place and person.

First year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						
Second year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						

3.3 On a scale from 1 to 5 (5 being excellent), how would you rate the surveillance systems' performance with regard to simplicity? Please mark the appropriate box with an X.

Could you briefly describe why this rating reflects the performance of the surveillance with regard to simplicity?

Simplicity: the system's structure and ease of operation.

First year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						
Second year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						

3.4 On a scale from 1 to 5 (5 being excellent), how would you rate the surveillance systems' performance with regard to flexibility? Please mark the appropriate box with an X.

Could you briefly describe why this rating reflects the performance of the surveillance with regard to flexibility?

Flexibility: the ability to adapt to changing information needs or technological operating conditions.

First year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						
Second year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						

3.5 On a scale from 1 to 5 (5 being excellent), how would you rate the surveillance systems' performance with regard to acceptability? Please mark the appropriate box with an X.

Could you briefly describe why this rating reflects the performance of the surveillance with regard to acceptability?

Acceptability: the willingness of persons and organisations to participate in the system.

First year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						
Second year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						

3.6 On a scale from 1 to 5 (5 being excellent), how would you rate the surveillance systems' performance with regard to stability? Please mark the appropriate box with an X.

Could you briefly describe why this rating reflects the performance of the surveillance with regard to stability?

Stability: the system's reliability (ability to collect, manage and provide data without failure) and availability (ability to be operational when needed).

First year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						
Second year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						

3.7 On a scale from 1 to 5 (5 being excellent), how would you rate the surveillance systems' performance with regard to sustainability? Please mark the appropriate box with an X.

Could you briefly describe why this rating reflects the performance of the surveillance with regard to sustainability?

Sustainability; the ongoing maintenance and support of a routine epidemiologic and/or virological surveillance system.

First year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						
Second year	5	4	3	2	1	
Excellent						Poor
Evaluation						

3.8 Considering the whole process within I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care SARS-CoV-2 surveillance (of data extraction, validation, pooling and reporting in the bulletin) could you reflect on the performance of this process? You may consider the performance attributes (data quality, timeliness, representativeness, simplicity, flexibility, acceptability, stability, and sustainability) or other.

2. Adaptions of COVID-19 primary care/outpatient surveillance

3.9 If you consider the current SARS-CoV-2 surveillance system configuration compared with the state of affairs in summer **2021**, what were the major adaptions to the system, if any?

3.10 What were the main drivers of adaptions that were made in the second half of **2021**?

4 Support during the project

4.1 Was data collection according to the protocol feasible? What facilitators and barriers were encountered (you may think of administrative burden, resources available, data management, any other)

4.2 What support did or do you need, if any, from the project coordinator, to enable data collection and data provision to the project?

4.3 Did participation in the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project yield any leverage for SARS-CoV-2 primary care surveillance aims at international level or regional/national level in your country?

5 Reflections and recommendations for future preparedness of respiratory sentinel surveillance

5.1 Has the SARS-CoV-2 surveillance system that was put in place been evaluated?

- If yes, could you indicate whether the evaluation was at one point in time, more often or continuous?

- And could you describe on what attributes the system was evaluated, what lessons could be learnt, and how these lessons were or will be implemented?

5.2 What are, in your point of view, the main challenges for sustainability of sentinel surveillance systems in your country, and in the broader European context?

5.3 What would you recommend to ensure preparedness of respiratory sentinel surveillance for future outbreaks?

6 SWOT analysis of the I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care surveillance project

Could you indicate what Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats you observe if you think of the primary care surveillance in the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project?

<p>Strengths (internal project organisation) <i>(What went well in the project? What was the added value of the project compared to other studies? What knowledge and resources were unique to this project?)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• .• .	<p>Weaknesses (internal project organisation) <i>(What needed improvement within the project, to learn from for future projects. What knowledge and resources were lacking?)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• .• .
<p>Opportunities (external, not controllable by the project organisation) <i>(What trends did the project take advantage of? What unanticipated information need did the project meet?)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• .• .	<p>Threats (external, not controllable by the project organisation) <i>(What did other studies/ surveillance systems do better in meeting information needs (e.g. from ECDC)? What was the project unprepared for?)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• .• .

Do you have any other thoughts or suggestions you would like to share?

Thank you very much for your reflections and time!
